

The Viscosity of Titanium Dioxide Sol in Presence of Electrolytes.

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Viscosity has been recognised as an important property which is very sensitive to changes in a colloidal system. It has been utilised for the study of three important characteristics of colloidal systems, *viz.*, (i) the change which takes place during gelation, (ii) the rate of coagulation and (iii) the degree of hydration of the colloidal particles.

Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 391) and Prasad, Mehta and Desai (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 1384) measured the viscosity of certain gel-forming mixtures to recognise different stages in the process of gelation. They explained the variation in viscosity on the changes in hydration of the colloid particles. Fernau and Pauli (*Kolloid Z.*, 1917, **20**, 20), Ostwald (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1913, **9**, 35) and Dhar and co-workers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, **38**, 253 ; 1928, **44**, 225 ; 1929, **48**, 43 ; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 1646) have all pointed out that the electrical charges carried by the colloid particles determine the degree of hydration of the particles and the changes in viscosity of a sol. Hatschek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1920, **27**, 163) has shown how the hydration factor of a colloid particle can be calculated from the results on the measurements of viscosity.

Freundlich and Ishizaka (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1913, **9**, 66), Pauli (*ibid.*, p. 64), Smoluchowski (*Kolloid Z.*, 1916, **18**, 190), Kawamura (*J. Coll. Sci. Imp. Univ. Tokyo*, 1908, **8**, 25) and numerous other investigators have used viscosity to measure the rate of coagulation of a sol. Gann (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1916, **8**, 64) who measured the changes in viscosity of aluminium oxide sol in presence of different amounts of electrolytes found that the autocatalytic nature of coagulation can be inferred from the viscosity-time curves.

Recently Joshi and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 329, 589 ; 1934, **11**, 173) have shown that autocatalysis though prevalent under certain conditions cannot be considered as a general characteristic of the coagulation phenomenon. They have also shown that on the addition of electrolytes, the viscosity shows an

initial diminution followed by a slow increase and that the viscosity-time curves *are not continuous* but show well marked breaks (Joshi and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329 ; 1934, 11, 133, 555, 573, 797). Patel and Desai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 26, 177) have found that the purity and the concentration of the colloid are necessary factors in determining the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation process. In the present investigation the changes in viscosity of titanium dioxide sol with time when electrolytes are added to the sol dialysed and diluted to different extents have been studied with a view to examine the validity of the above views.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The sol was prepared by the peptisation of titanium hydroxide by hydrochloric acid. The titanium hydroxide was first precipitated by adding ammonium hydroxide and then washed with hot water till free from ammonia. It was suspended in a large volume of water and boiled. At intervals, 2N-hydrochloric acid was added till the sol was quite clear. The volume of the sol was kept constant by replacing the evaporated water from time to time. The sol was dialysed in a parchment bag in continuously running water, the level of water in the outside vessel being kept constant. During dialysis, no titanium was detected in the dialysate.

The colloid content of the sol was estimated by taking 25 c.c. of the sol and adding to it a concentrated solution of ammonium chloride in excess to coagulate it. The sol was heated on a water-bath at 70° to hasten coagulation. The precipitate was filtered, dried in an air-oven, ignited in a silica crucible and weighed as TiO_2 . The concentration of the sol was found to be 2.912 g. of colloidal TiO_2 per litre.

Scarpa's method (*Gazzetta*, 1919, 40, 271) modified by Farrow (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347) and improved upon by Prasad, Mehta and Desai (*loc. cit.*) was used. The viscometer along with the guard tube was enclosed in an electrically heated thermostat maintained at $33^\circ \pm 0.02^\circ$.

The apparatus being standardised, 10 c.c. of the sol were introduced into the viscometer and suction at a pressure of 15 cm. of water, which was kept constant throughout the investigation, was applied. When the level of the liquid reached the lower mark, a stop-watch was started and the time of rise, t_1 from the lower to the upper mark was

noted. The viscometer was next connected to the atmosphere and the time of fall, t_2 , from the upper to the lower mark was also noted. The viscosity of the sol was calculated from the formula,

$$\eta = K \left(\frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2} \right)$$

where K is a constant which was determined by finding out $t_1 t_2 / t_1 + t_2$ for pure water whose absolute coefficient of viscosity at 33° is known and it was found to be 0.001136.

For coagulation 5 c.c. of the sol were taken in a test tube and in another the requisite amount of the electrolyte was diluted to 5 c.c. by adding distilled water. The total volume of the sol+electrolyte was always 10 c.c.

FIG. 1.

AlCl_3 and undialysed sol.

When the electrolyte was added to the sol, a second watch was started. This gave the time since mixing at which the time of rise and fall in the viscometer was measured. The mean of the time at which the mixture was made to rise and that at which it reached the lower mark while falling, was reckoned as the time at which the viscosity reading of the mixture was taken.

The electrolytes employed were the chlorides of potassium, magnesium and aluminium. Their concentrations were so selected that the time required for coagulation was about an hour and a quarter. The original sol is designated *A* and the twice and four times diluted ones, *A/2* and *A/4*. All the results are not given; only a few selected ones are shown graphically in Fig. 1-3 for illustration.

FIG. 2.

KCl + sol dialysed for 9 days.

FIG. 8.

*A-sol dialysed for 20 days.*I— AlCl_3 : II— MgCl_2 : III— KCl .

The p_H of the various samples of the sol was determined by the indicator method. 10 C.c. of the sol were coagulated by potassium chloride (0.5 g.) and 1 c.c. of bromophenol-blue was added to the supernatant liquid. The tint thus obtained was compared with that of the standards prepared from the B.D.H. universal buffer mixture. The values of p_H thus obtained did not differ from those obtained with the sol using Walpole's comparator method.

The electrical conductivity of each of the samples was also determined by Kohlrausch's method. The results are given in the following table in which k denotes specific conductivity.

TABLE I.

Specific conductivity and p_H .

Sol dialysed for	A		A/2		A/4	
	$k \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$k \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$k \times 10^3$.	p_H .
0 days	34.56	2.4	18.07	2.5	9.35	2.6
3	7.26	2.8	3.77	3.1	2.02	3.3
6	3.84	3.0	1.96	3.3	1.55	3.7
9	3.12	3.5	1.68	3.7	1.33	3.9
12	2.45	3.7	1.51	3.8	1.23	4.9
15	1.96	4.0	1.37	4.2	1.10	4.3
20	1.79	4.1	1.19	4.3	0.98	4.4
25	1.63	4.2	1.08	4.5	0.85	4.8

DISCUSSION.

It will be seen from the curves in Fig. 1—3 that the viscosity of the titanium dioxide sol to which an electrolyte is added increases with time. This increase in viscosity may be due to (i) an increase in size of the colloid particles due to coagulation and (ii) an increase in their hydration due to a diminution in their electric charge. But it is to be observed that the curves obtained with this sol dialysed only for a few days are *periodic* and do not show a continuous increase in viscosity with time. As the sol gets purer due to continued dialysis, the *periodic* nature of the curves disappears. This fact is illustrated in the following table in which P, P₁, P₂ and P₃ represent diminishing periodicity in the curves and N denotes its absence.

TABLE II.

Sol dialysed for	KCl			MgCl ₂			AlCl ₃		
	A.	A/2.	A/4.	A.	A/2.	A/4.	A.	A/2.	A/4.
0 days	P	P	P ₂	P ₂	P ₃	P ₃	P ₃	P ₃	P ₃
3	P	P	P ₂	P ₂	P ₃	P ₃	P ₃	P ₃	N
6	P ₁	P ₁	P ₂	P ₂	P ₃	N	P ₃	P ₃	N
9	P ₁	P ₁	P ₂	N	N	N	N	N	N
12	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
15	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
20	N	N	—	N	N	—	N	N	—
25	N	—	—	N	—	—	N	—	—

This sort of *periodic* or discontinuous nature of the viscosity-time curves was also observed by Joshi and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) in the coagulation of arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide and certain lyophobic sols. The results obtained in this investigation are an independent confirmation of the observations of the above investigators.

The above table also illustrates that the discontinuous nature of the curves becomes less marked as the sol is diluted. With $A/4$ sols the discontinuity in the curves is hardly perceptible. This is in accordance with the observations of the above investigators who found that the viscosity-time curves are periodic or discontinuous in the slow region of coagulation. The coagulation of particular samples of the sol by the same amount of an electrolyte is more rapid, the greater the dilution.

It will be noticed in Table II that the discontinuous nature of the viscosity-time curves is more marked with potassium chloride than with magnesium chloride or aluminium chloride. This may be attributable to the increased rate of coagulation of the sol with the latter electrolytes.

Table I shows that the specific conductivity and hydrogen ion concentration of the sol diminish both on dilution and dialysis. It would appear that this accounts for the rapidity of coagulation with dilution and dialysis which is a consequence of the decrease of the peptising ions.

The autocatalytic nature of the coagulation process as demonstrated by the "S" shape of the viscosity-time curves disappears as the sol is progressively dialysed: the curves for the sol dialysed for nine days or more do not have an "S" shape. This is in confirmation of the observations made in the previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **11**, 177) that the purity of the sol plays an important part in determining the autocatalytic nature of its coagulation.

SUMMARY.

1. The changes in viscosity of the titanium dioxide sol, dialysed and diluted to different extents, with time when electrolytes are added to it have been studied using Scarpa's method with modifications.

2. It is found that the viscosity of the sol increases with time and that the viscosity-time curves are periodic or discontinuous in the slow region. This is in agreement with the observations of Joshi and co-workers.

3. The specific conductivity and hydrogen ion concentration of the sol diminish both on dilution and dialysis thus accounting for the rapidity of coagulation as a consequence of the decrease of the peptising ions.

4. The autocatalytic nature of the coagulation process as demonstrated by the "S" shape of the viscosity-time curves disappears as the sol is progressively dialysed in confirmation of the observations made in a previous communication by the authors.

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A Modified Photographic Method for Substances of Small Rotatory Dispersion.

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The method usually adopted for measuring optical rotatory dispersion in the ultraviolet is to pass light from a polychromatic source through a spectro-polarimeter and take photographs for various settings of the analyser (Lowry, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1908, **A**, 81, 472). The wave-length at which extinction takes place is measured when the polarimeter consists simply of two nicols as polariser and analyser or, and this is the more usual case, in the case of a two-field instrument, the wave-length having equal intensity in the two halves of the spectrum is determined. In practice it is found that instead of a single wave-length being extinguished at a time, a dark band is obtained the width of which is determined by numerous factors such as the rotatory dispersion of the material under investigation, the magnitude of its rotation, the dispersion of the spectrograph used and the intensity distribution of the light source. The wave-length of the middle point of the band is taken as the required wave-length corresponding to the analyser setting but this is obviously unsatisfactory because of the usual shape of the rotatory dispersion curves. The error involved, however, will be negligible if the band is quite